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ISLAMISATION OF EUROPE: CONSTRUCTIVISM AND „GRAND REPLACEMENT“ – BETWEEN FICTION AND FACTION

Abstract: *In the past decades, the world has witnessed expansive migrations of mostly Islamic population from African and Middle Eastern countries to European soil. Is this a natural process of global movement of people from Muslim-majority countries followed by inevitable demographic and cultural changes or is it a strategic realisation of Camus' prophetic „grand remplacement“ theory? By placing relevant works of fiction (Raspail, Brodel, Houellebecq, Camus, Rushdie, Lučić) into the context of political constructivism and synthetic nation building theory (Đurković, Kalajić, Ekmečić), the author intends to deconstruct the concept of nation building adopted and further developed by world powers for reasons of strengthening their geopolitical position, at the expense of weakening national countries and keeping them in the state of constant internal conflict. It will become conclusive that there is a growing tendency of abusing religion for the purpose of constructing a new national identity (new world order).*

Keywords: *islamisation, constructivism, nationalism, fiction, prose-lytism, grand replacement.*

1. Introduction

People have always moved from one place to another, either across national borders (external migration) or within a country (internal migration). Reasons were multiple, including a pursuit of better economic opportunities, or forced displacement due to various calamities (wars, earthquakes, floods). History has shown that such human migrations can significantly change the

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demographic structure of the world, and its socio-political card. Recent Biblical exodus of mostly Islamic people from the third world countries to Europe (mostly, France and Germany), has made various theorists look for causative roots of such a dynamic trend. Careful and extensive research of this phenomenon has led to the creation of various theories as to the reasons of continuous, persistent and permanent transcontinental movement of people of different race, colour and creed.

Le Grand Remplacement (Great Replacement) theory created by a French writer Renaud Camus, proves to be the most intriguing and analytically challenging. It inspired theorists from various disciplines to put into their analytical focus the concept of nation building or constructivism, and to ponder upon the nature of the process of its creation. Consequently, political thinkers and geopolitical historians have gradually polarised the world of cognizance into proponents of natural and synthetic nation building theories. Constructivists have a scientific and moral obligation to justify their point of view by rationalising the purpose of constructing a new nation, who gains most from reconstructing Europe into a community of regions or quasi-nations, and how seriously Europe's authentic national identity is being threatened by the Islamic revolt. By consulting the works and ideas of authorities from various related disciplines (history, political theory, literature), the theory of synthetic nation building will show its close relatedness to migrations, Islam, constructivism, national identity, Europe of regions, and a *grand remplacement* theory that needs further confronting with its alternative, a *grand deplacement* theory, in order to better understand the future of Europe and its indigenous population. Another important question that requires doctrinarian approach is the role of Islamic religion in the process of building Europe of regions. A new European order without unlimited sovereignty and centralism of nation states; Europe made of autonomous regions based on the principle of subsidiarity can clearly be seen evolving on the political horizon.¹

¹ Given that in elaboration of the topic, the author intends to interchangeably use terms “ethnos”, “nation” and “people” as different socio-political phenomena, their true meaning needs clarification. Namely, the word „ethnos” denotes a cultural or ethnic community often identifying with each other through shared blood ties and behavior patterns, while „nation” often includes a more complex set of cultural, historical, and political elements, and can be seen as a larger or more formalised concept than an ethnos. The word „people” is the most general term, encompassing both specific ethnic groups (ethnoi) and larger national communities. (the Author's note).

2. Constructivism and synthetic nation-building theory (Ekmečić, Kalajić, Đurković)

*“There is no prosperity in a state that has no notion of sin and shame.”
(Konchalovski, Russian historian)*

In 2010, Alan-Gérard Slama, the *Figaro* columnist, wrote the following:

“Are our old democracies, faced with economic, social, demographic and intellectual shock without precedent in the past 70 years, in danger of taking the path comparable to tribal and arbitrary (political) models that impede the development of the majority of the third world countries?” (Novi standard/Mortimer, 2023).²

This was Slama’s prophetic reaction to yet another financial crisis that hit France, and the rest of Europe, pushing it toward “Third-Worldism (fr. *tiersmondisation*)”. Western order was seriously undermined by Gaddafi’s overthrow in 2011, which led to the first migrant crisis. Angela Merkel provoked the second crisis when she opened European borders in 2015 to more than a million migrants. Muslim terrorism had already left behind hundreds of dead people and progressivist radicalism inflamed identity tensions.

We see that the concept of nation and national identity has become the centre of international/global conflict of opinion. Scholars have polarised the existentialistic relation toward nation as a political and philosophical phenomenon. Naturalists believe that a nation has been built for centuries in a chronic process of evolution of three factors: collective self-recognition of the uniqueness of character; social institutions that express an authentic lifestyle; and a capacity to form such continuity (Tremblay, 1993: 111-126). After World War II, the UN Charter guaranteed all peoples the right to self-determination within their territorial borders.³ However, ever since African colonies gained their independence in 1960s and created their own sovereign states, this principle no longer corresponded to geopolitical reality

² Novi Standard/Mortimer, G. (2023). Francuska u procesu “trećesvetizacije”. (prev. Miloš Milojević), *Novi standard*. 30 јуна 2023; <https://standard.rs/2023/06/30/francuska-u-procesu-trecesvetizacije/?alphabet=latin>

³ Article 1 para. 2 of the United Nations Charter (1945). <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter/full-text#:text=promoting%20international%20co%2Doperation%20in%20the%20political%20field,as%20to%20race%2C%20sex%2C%20language%2C%20or%20religion> (accessed on 10 September 2025).

(Deutsch, 1963: Foreword) since African people were spilt over their national borders into European soil through massive migration processes. In addition, Cold War enabled the acknowledgement of the right to self-determination to certain regions that separated from their mother states (e.g. Croatia).⁴ These regions contained ethnic component as a building block. However, scholars associated with the theory of nation building, failed to put into focus ethnic diversity as a primary characteristic of many national states, giving way to common (national) identity uniting all inhabitants of the state, regardless of ethnic heritage (Connor, 1972: 320).

According to Ekmečić, the idea of Europe of regions was developed in Germany. Linguistically, the phrase was coined by general de Gaulle who believed that, if the idea of nation were to be extended across the French borders, France could attract the Flemish people of Belgium and Holland, the Alemanni from the Rhine Province, Switzerland and Austria, and perhaps the Celts from Spain and Great Britain, and their common constituents would not be language or territory (*ius solis*) but ancestry (*ius sanguinis*) (Ekmečić, 2002: 19-74).

This insistence on micronationalisms was a natural consequence of the inability of a democratic state to support and promote certain values, including ethnic diversity, which is not fit for state integration. Modern history gives valuable examples of what happens to a multiethnic state (e.g. former Yugoslavia, the Soviet Union) if it fails to perceive the particularities of each ethnic group and give it credit. Ethnic diversity gives ample ground for manipulation and nation destruction. In other words, national state stands in the way to future global society. Without a collective European identity, it is not possible to create a joint federative European state.

Regionalisation of Europe as a geopolitical concept aims at annulling national sovereignty and territoriality. By giving power and voice to ethnic groups, the concept of nation and national identity becomes unnecessary. The European Union has become the largest experiment in terms of denationalizing its member states and unifying and integrating ethnic communities. Instead, European spirit of collectiveness builds identity through various decrees, the system of mutual dependence of national currencies, and the power of banks over society. The entire project is orchestrated by multinational companies and Western powers with the help of invasive technologization of society. Such calculative thinking and instrumentalism that characterize the age of modernism and technological essence inevitably lead to a

⁴ In December 1991, Germany unilaterally recognized the independence of Croatia making the EEC to take the same stand (Crawford, 1996: 491).

forgetfulness of Being, loss of identity and reduction of the world and humans to mere resources (Heidegger, 1977:4).

If the new European community is to be construed of regions, what would be their common denominator if not language, religion or territory? For Ekmečić, that would be culture as a trans-territorial category (Ekmečić, 2002: 19-74). However, Theodor Adorno claimed that culture as a social phenomenon can easily be misunderstood for race. Adorno's resistance to national identity and nation was particularly evident in his late works. As a German Jew under Nazi regime, Adorno was forced into exile, which made him later reject German appeals to national culture and particularity. In an attempt to understand the complexities of race and identity in a modern world, Adorno created the concept of culture industry, arguing that mass media and popular culture create a deceptive unity under liberal capitalism. His philosophy highlights how the manipulation of culture can serve to legitimize particularities like race, while simultaneously seeking to retain a concept of universalism that resists oppressive ideologies (Adorno, 1991: 61-98). Culture industry is depriving an individual of personal autonomy understood in Kantian way, as the maturity and the capacity to exercise one's own discretionary judgment, and to make up one's own mind for oneself (Kant, 2004: 34). Thus, standardized mindset of an ethnic group or a set of ethnic groups assimilated through culture can be easily manipulated by impersonal, external forces, over which individuals have little control, if deprived of the autonomy of will. Deutsch contended that ethnic identity based on cultural homogeneity would prove no match for the power of self-interest (Deutsch, 1966: 86-107).

Political constructivists are persistent to relativise the significance of national state and its role in internal and external relations; instead, they insist on promoting synthetically construed micronational creations that can be easily decomposed, after fulfilling their purpose. However, what ethnically-composed quasi-nations cannot provide includes a political space for creating the feeling of belonging, individual rights framework and legal subjectivity in international relations. Today, pro-nationalistic voices are becoming louder and more resonant in Europe. As a proponent of the nationalistic idea, Ekmečić concludes his thesis on constructivism and synthetic nation building rather optimistically, claiming that survival of a nation is possible, but it depends on the fall of liberal capitalism and free market, on the protection of national market and consumer rights, as well as on the limitation of labour mobility (Ekmečić, 2002: 73-74). In elaboration of his theory of synthetic nation-building, he gave special attention to religion, as an important factor in the construction process. His idea is strongly supported by many

scholars, including Vladeta Jerotić, who claimed that national and religious aspect are integral constitutive element of every people (Jerotić, 1999). Such religious type of national movement in modern geopolitical history creates stronger effect on society than any profane idea. Synthetic nations construed on religious ideology tend to divert into fundamentalism, which can be the case with Islamic communities.

According to Đurković, national identity plays a very important role in practical geopolitics of Western powers (i.e. corporations). It is mostly used as an instrument for construction or destruction of a national group, in order to achieve economic interest and geopolitical dominance. Popularisation of queer identities (be it man, community or nation) is strategically performed in order to destabilise the integrity of a particular entity and put it under control of great corporations, secret organisations or world powers. Unlike Ekmečić, Đurković does not limit the source of instrumentalisation of constructivism to Vatican and Germany, but rather blames the Western leading countries for abusing the concept of regional identity to create quasination-alisms, thus weakening ethnic substance, geographic control and geopolitical interests of other nations and states. Đurković further contends that these interest groups have diligently studied the historical development of nation, as a geopolitical phenomenon, in order to synthesise an instant nation that would evolve into a regional quasi-state, which threatens to undermine stability, democracy and international relations of national states (Đurković, 2024: 7-34). He claims that it is important to understand the danger of double and multiple identities, when ethnic identity is accepted simultaneously with regional identity, which is recognised as a political as much as cultural phenomenon. Utopian models of multiple identities promoted inside the European Union represent a serious threat to future stability of the European countries and their national identity concept. In that sense, Đurković emphasises the importance of Ekmečić's insisting on uncovering the idea of Europe of regions, since it leads toward undermining national identity and state sovereignty (Đurković, 2024:33).

A new experiment of the Western powers to infiltrate millions of Muslims into European states and nations in order to further spread liberal capitalism has become the focus of scholarly attention of Dragoš Kalajić. As a liberal thinker and moralist, Kalajić's observant eye sees that European political architects are keen on reconstructing a national society into a society of citizens with unconscious subservient mentality. Why is Europe insisting on indulging in the concept of a cosmopolitan, a citizen who solely protects his own rights and interests? Such an individual corresponds more to the demands of liberal capitalism. A citizen of the world is an agent of imperial-

ism. Insistence on erasing all otherness has made the world show little interest in the complex economic and political forces that provoke migration. National society, as an organic community of individuals grouped around the same ethnic, ethical, cultural, and spiritual values resists the temptations of the world market in order to protect its own national interests (Калајић, 1994:105). Since the idea of nation is standing in the way to liberal capitalism, it is necessary to disband it and then use the minority fragments to serve the constructivist process of nation-building. One way of destroying a nation is through demographic implosion (regression of birthrate), which stands in contrast to demographic explosion (progression of birthrate) of Islamic nations, who blindly follow the revelations of Islam.

Regression of birthrate has hit almost all European nations and ethnoi to the extent of democide of Europeans (white people), while Islamic countries are experiencing a demographic boom. According to Kalajić, reasons are multiple, including wide propagation of contraception methods and means, liberalisation of abortion, spread of homosexuality, subjection to the demands of consumerism and egoism, or open war of leading powers against the foundation of human society: family and motherhood (Калајић, 1994: 171-173). Why are Europeans so susceptible to external conditioning? The answer lies in the absolute and inviolable authority of an individual that is being promoted through culture industry. If such authority is not limited, Europe will face Thirdworldism, or *grand replacement*.

With traditional or modern leftist parties domineering the European political scene, internationalistic tendencies that give priority to hungry masses of the Third world over well fed Europeans will keep the door to Europe open to all migration waves coming from the South. Furthermore, every attempt to avoid *grand replacement* future of Europe eventually ends in reverse racism. Weak thought philosophers, such as Gianni Vattimo, see regression in fertility rate as the way to reduce social problems, and that shift in ethnoi and nations is a natural process that is beyond suppression (Vattimo, 2004). Kalajić resolutely rejects such anti-European racist ideas without sparing the words for their advocates. In support of a nationalistic thought that, he contends, will surpass internationalism, Kalajić reminds the academic public of Emil Cioran's utterance that "*the very possibility of such a heterogeneous society shows that, in that region, the autochthonous do not have the slightest desire to preserve their identity. When people lose the historic idea of their mission in this world – they have no reason to preserve their difference, to maintain their features in the middle of chaos of faces*" (Калајић, 1994: 175).

3. Islamisation and migrations (France, Germany)

There is an ongoing debate among scholars regarding the perceived growing influence of Islam within Europe, often driven by Muslim immigration, which is seen as a demographic, cultural, or political shift. While historical Islam has long been present in parts of Europe, the modern discourse of Islamisation focuses on postbellum immigration and its impact on European societies. Concerns include the integration of Muslim communities, potential conflicts between different cultural and religious values, and the extent to which Islamic practices (such as Sharia law) might challenge democratic principles and European legal frameworks. Predominantly secular Western European countries, especially France and Germany, have developed a valid concern over the prospect of transformation of modern democratic and liberal societies back into religiously-restrained patriarchal communities.

In order to better understand the threat that hypothetically comes from Islam as one of the three largest world confessions, it is necessary to look into its phenomenology. Islam is a complex religious phenomenon as it simultaneously encompasses both ethnic and confessional component (Кошутин, 2002: 274). Ethnic component is closely related to the Arabic population settled at the Arabic peninsula. Although Islam tends to be a religion with a universal dimension, it remains closely tied to its Arabic roots. Firstly, Qur'an, the book of Allah's revelations to prophet Mohammed, is written in Arabic and cannot be translated into any other language, but has to be read in its original. The book can only be interpreted or paraphrased into other languages. Although Arabic in its nature and character, Islam as a confessional religion can be compared to other religions, such as Christianity or Buddhism (James, 1961: 203-207).

Modern understanding of the word *Islam* is twofold. Firstly, it can be understood as a system of beliefs, a monotheistic religion. Secondly, it is a civilisation under the influence of religion. Today's efforts of Islamic modernists to put an end to the past and turn Islam into a modern concept of belief adjusted to European technology and institutions have been seriously and continuously undermined by loud voices of the return to the pure roots of Islam from the times of prophet Mohammed, known as Neoislam/Islamic fundamentalism⁵ or Revivalism (Кошутин, 2002: 277; Ћosić, 2008: 101).

⁵ The author generally tends to agree with J. Esposito and his dislike for the word fundamentalism to be used in a pejorative and derogatory way. In context with Islam, a fundamentalist is described as an advocate of literal interpretation of the book of God (Qur'an), a political activist, radicalist, extremist, fanatic, and a terrorist (Esposito, 1999: 6). Scientific truth requires revealing many faces and postures of Islam, and not a monolithic approach.

According to this understanding, there is no similarity between Islam and democracy, since democracy assumes freedom and equality of citizens, their political subjectivity, political plurality, difference in opinion, and tolerance, separation of the church and state, and other economic, political and cultural values. It is believed the revitalisation of Muslim governments and societies, which are in a serious decline, requires reimplementation of Islamic Sharia law. Yet, there are some western Islamologists who believe in democratisation of Islam, under the condition of reviewing the status of non-Muslim minorities promoted by a classical Islamic doctrine. Namely, a long history of distrust, criticism and condemnation has turned the image of Islam into a militant, expansionist and rabidly anti-European religion that threatens to destroy humanistic values on which a modern democratic society lies (Esposito, 1999: 5-6).

Similarly, it is difficult to separate Sharia law from Islamic religion, since both represent the word of God (Allah). Islam and Sharia law equally regulate profane and sacral issues; hence, Islam is not familiar with the idea of a citizen, as a participant in a political process (Ćosić, 2008: 100). Mohamed E. Hamdi claims that secularism can only be sustained in the Islamic world with the help of local Islamic dictators helped by the Western powers (Hamdi, 1996: 84-5).

Traditional Islam was established in parts of Europe through the Umayyad conquest of Hispania (7-10th centuries) and later by the Ottoman Empire's expansion into Southeastern Europe. However, by the end of the 15th century, the Muslim populations in areas like Spain were largely expelled or converted to Christianity.

Modern views on the Muslim migration trend have been mostly negative, and in ignorance of the complex economic and political forces that provoked it. Very few scholars do realise that immigration constitutes an undeniably negative phenomenon, in part because it turns immigrants into victims, by erasing their roots (de Benoist and Champetier, 2000: ch. 3, art. 3).

Hence, a more fitting general terms would be Islamic revivalism, or Islamic activism, which have roots within the Islamic tradition. In recent years, the terms, such as political Islam and Islamism have also become a commonplace.

3.1. Islamisation of France

“I’m at home here, not you.”

(R. Camus)

The presence of Muslim population in France is closely related to the French colonial invasion of North African territories, primarily Tunisia, Morocco, and Algeria in the mid-19th century.⁶ While many Muslims integrated well, African Muslims are facing serious challenges, including racial discrimination, debates over secularism (*laïcité*), and a rising far-right presence that targets Muslims. There are also internal tensions between mainstream Muslim practices and the influence of radical ideologies like the Muslim Brotherhood.⁷ Thus, *le Monde* has recently reported that according to a confidential government report, the Muslim Brotherhood poses a long-term threat to France’s national cohesion, not through violence but by gradually eroding secular values at the local level (Le Monde, 2025a).⁸ Such political Islamism risks affecting the public sphere and local politics by creating increasingly numerous Islamist ecosystems.

French government is concerned about the subversive nature of the low-level Islamism project aimed at turning the entire French society to Sharia law. However, except this report, there are no other documents that demonstrate the desire of Muslims in France to establish an Islamic state in France or to enforce Sharia law there. The *Le Monde* further states that the Muslim Brotherhood, alias Muslims of France, are not committed to “aggressive separatism” but more likely to “subtle yet no less subversive aim for the institutions” (Le Monde, 2025b).⁹ To avoid such a scenario, France must launch a

⁶ France has the largest Muslim population in Europe, with several million people of Muslim background, though precise figures are unavailable due to French privacy laws.

⁷ The Muslim Brotherhood is a transnational Sunni Islamist movement founded in Egypt in 1928 as a religious, social, and political organization aiming to create a pan-Islamic caliphate. The movement’s ideology posits that Islam is a comprehensive way of life, and not just a religious observance. Some European countries, such as Austria, have banned the MB, classifying it as an organization linked to religiously motivated crime. A very strong and highly engaged Muslim organization in France is the Muslims of France (*Musulmans de France*, former *Union des organisations islamiques de France* - UOIF), which responds to religious, cultural, educational, social and humanitarian needs of the Muslims of France (Qubaisi, 2025).

⁸ Le Monde/AFT (2025a), French report warns of spread of Muslim Brotherhood ideology. *Le Monde*. 21 May 2025; https://www.lemonde.fr/en/france/article/2025/05/21/french-report-warns-of-subtle-but-subversive-spread-of-muslim-brotherhood-ideology_6741471_7.html (accessed on 8 Sept. 2025)

⁹ Le Monde/AFT (2025b). Macron urges government action on Muslim Brotherhood’s

public awareness campaign along with the promotion of a secular discourse and send a strong and positive signal to the Muslim community, like the teaching of Arabic language.

French scholars indicate that violence which has been wrought in the name of Islam in France, against French citizens, will prevail if the organisation of this religion does not undergo a profound process of understanding by the French citizens. Perpetual quarrels regarding the display of Islamic symbols in public places (the burkini being the latest example) cannot be the only policy response to Jihadism and religious fundamentalism. To address the issue, the Montaigne Institute carried out an unprecedented survey, together with the French Institute of Public Opinion (IFOP), which yielded some valuable results (Karoui, 2016: 7). This large-scale survey has shown that a majority of Muslims in France adhere to a system of values and a religious practice which can seamlessly co-exist within the corpus of the French Republic and nation. However, it has also revealed that there are many young Muslims whose sense of identity is first and foremost tied to religion (religious identity). They stand firm in the belief that the more fundamentalist they are, the more Muslims they are, and thus the more themselves they are (Karoui, 2016: *ibid*). By denying them the right to express publicly their religious identity, secular France has actually helped ignite religious fundamentalism (Al-Jazeera/Hafez, 2025).¹⁰

Thus, the survey reveals the co-existence of two very different realities: one is a silent majority of practicing Muslims who have no major conflict with French societal norms, and a minority drawn to Islamic fundamentalism. Furthermore, the survey has shown that French government has not managed thus far to organise Islam in France, nor has it taken any measures in order to tackle the influence of the Muslim Brotherhood movement and the spread of political Islamism in France. Reasons for such a failure are multiple, including geopolitical restraints, considering that the organisation of a French Islam is entangled in the complex relations that France has developed with both North Africa and Turkey (Karoui, 2016: 7). Another obstacle is the non-existence of the Muslim community in France. No sense of belonging, shared interests, or capacity for coordinated action have been detected. Financial restraint implies that Islam in France is under-funded, and non-

influence in France. *Le Monde*. 21 May 2025; https://www.lemonde.fr/en/france/article/2025/05/21/macron-urges-government-action-on-muslim-brotherhood-s-influence-in-france_6741505_7.html (accessed on 8.9.2025)

¹⁰ Al-Jazeera/Hafez, F. (2025). State-sponsored Islamophobia in France encourages violence. *Aljazeera*. 5 July 2025. <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2025/7/5/state-sponsored-islamophobia-in-france-encourages-violence>

transparent, thus lacking the capacity to collect donations from followers, which harms its reputation. However, the strongest obstacle is institutional because the French government is not placing enough trust in the Muslims living in France (Karoui, 2016: 8). Namely, French far-right populist parties stake their political motivations in highly exclusionary nativism, which most frequently targets foreign-born populations. Although these parties are not directly the cause of Islamophobic sentiments, their existence has catalysed the integration of radical right politics into the regular sociopolitical climate in France. French populists have thrived on these anti-immigration sentiments (“an immigrant is a symbol of loss of sovereignty/civilisational identity”; “it is important to have been born here to truly be one of us” – RN, Marine Le Pen) by taking back national control and by manipulating the composition of population through immigration restrictions (Garand, 2019: 23-29) and by proposing radical measures which are to prevent any spread of extremist Islamist ideas that threaten national cohesion (Le Monde, 2025a).

Building a French Islam in such a resistive setting is possible but it is full of challenges. A new reality of Islam in France must be put forward. Namely, the majority of Muslims are born in France and three-quarters of them are French nationals. The key to creating a modern approach to Islamic religion is to accept a new sociological evolution, which will make a balance between the over-representation of Muslim labourers, low-ranking employees and the unemployed compared to the national average, and a well-educated and professionally well-integrated Muslim elite that are being attracted through selective immigration (Karoui, 2016: 64).

How does the migration trend affect the creation of the French Islam? The OECD 2024 Migration Report reveals a record-high level of immigrations to OECD countries. In 2022, France received 294,000 new immigrants on a long-term or permanent basis, which is 10% more than in 2021. Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia were the top three nationalities of newcomers in 2022, with Morocco registering the strongest increase in flows to France (OECD Report, 2024: 208). These high flows have fuelled widespread concern about migrants’ impact on France’s economy and society, putting migration management and border control at the top of political agendas.

However, while France is putting forward the question of labour shortages and how to increase the accessibility and availability of labour market channels, what remains in the background is the cultural, and religious heritage that Muslim migrants carry to the host country. The economic aspect tends to overcome the cultural and national setting in France. Conflicts arising from cultural and religious differences between French citizens and Muslim

migrants are not the top priority for the French government currently preoccupied with ballooning budget deficit that threatens to freeze social and economic life in France (CNN/Vandoorne, 2025).¹¹

President Macron has been heavily criticised by the populist opposition (*Rassemblement National party*) for not taking any concrete action against rising political Islam in France, and has been held directly responsible for violent resistance of radical part of Muslim community to national laws and integration process (Le Monde, 2025b). As Huntington suggests, instead of building a multicultural society, France is facing a serious clash of cultures (Huntington, 1996: 200). Reasons are to be found in the fact that non-Western civilisations are no longer the exploited recipients of Western civilisation but have become additional important actors joining the West to shape and move world history (Huntington, 1996: 91-95).

In the past decades, migration has become a central political theme in France. French polls show that 70 percent of the population (French by ethnicity) want to tighten migration laws. Some analysts claim that France's migration-related angst is surprising for multiple reasons. Statistics show that French migration levels have been relatively modest in the past decades and on the lower end in Western Europe. Namely, from 2004 to 2024, average annual net migration was 1.33 per 1,000 people, as compared to 3.4 in Germany. In 2023, the net migration to France was 183,000 persons as compared to 663,000 across the Rhine (de Weck, 2025). These figures indicate that France is not even close to a migration crisis. Contrary to the general opinion, facts show that France has introduced very few affirmative action policies supporting ethnic minorities that could make France's majority white population feel disadvantaged. President Macron blames academics for advancing a politics of secession and division by "ethicising social questions". Determined to promote and protect cohesion and equality, French constitutional act prohibits the state from collecting data about race, ethnicity or religion, but that cannot paralyse the provoked racist reflexes in the French people. If mainstream media decide to debate over the warning statements of the chronicler of the hardships of aging men in the West that soon "entire territories of France will be under Islamist control", average Frenchman will believe them, without asking for substantiating evidence (de Weck, 2025).

¹¹ CNN World/Vandoorne, S. (2025). France's government has collapsed again. How did we get here and what's next? *CNN World*. 9 September 2025; <https://edition.cnn.com/2025/09/09/europe/frances-government-collapsed-whats-next-intl> (accessed on 10 September 2025).

3.2. Islamisation of Germany

Next to France, Germany has the largest Muslim population in Europe. Demographic data show a stable and continuous growth of the Muslim population due to immigration, higher birth rates, and some conversions, but it still remains a minority in Germany. To illustrate, in 2010 estimated Muslim population in Germany was 3.3 million or 4.1% (mostly Turkish guest workers); in 2016, the number of Muslim immigrants increased to less than 5 million or 6.1% (refugee surge from Syria, Iraq, Afghanistan); the 2022 census shows another increase of 5.5 million Muslims or 6.5 % (immigrants from African and Middle Eastern countries, plus converts and secular Muslims). By 2050, this number is expected to increase to 8-10 million (medium migration: balanced immigration plus fertility differences) or 17.5 million (high migration: unrestricted asylum plus family reunification) (Kaufman, 2023). These demographic data have turned the political concept of Islamisation into a most controversial topic in public discourse since the 2015 migrant crisis, fuelled by rapid immigration from Muslim-majority countries. Many critics warn that this could lead to a loss of secular, Christian-influenced identity, while multiculturalists see it as baseless alarmism that incites xenophobia.

Despite polarised views on massive inflow of Muslims into Germany, the question remains how it will affect German geopolitical and demographic setting. Although Germany's history with Islam (e.g. Ottoman alliances, Ottoman mosques) shows entanglement rather than invasion, the failed integration entails risks of Islamic extremism. There are political allegations that "legalist Islamism" is using democracy to subvert it (Berman, 2024). The greatest strategic challenge for German government would be to ensure that shared values (like secular law) prevail, without alienating communities.

How much has Germany contributed to the Islamophobic rhetoric and to spreading fear of Islamic fundamentalism among German non-Muslim citizens? According to Ramm, German state has contributed to "Islamising" Turkish immigrants through citizenship tests and integration policies that essentialise Islam as incompatible with secular values, fostering a divide between "Muslim/Turkish" and "Western/German" spheres. Such measures that Germany promotes and finds effective include remigration for failed asylum seekers (more than half) or school caps¹² on migrant enrolment (Ramm, 2010: 187). Against the background of persistent Islamophobia in

¹² School caps or enrollment caps refer to the maximum number of students a school can accommodate at either the entire school level or within a specific classroom, serving to manage overcrowding (author's note).

German society, the media have also contributed a great deal to reproducing problematic images of Islam. Findings show that 37% of the Islam-related articles in German print media discuss Islam in the context of terrorism, war and political unrest (Richter, Paasch-Colberg, 2023: 8).

Growing diversification of lifestyles and hybrid identifications among Turkish-Germans have culminated in the Muslim collective living in parallel societies (ghettos), social exclusion, educational shortcomings and forms of patriarchal violence (e.g. forced marriages or 'honour killings'). Such viewpoint seriously obstructs the process of integration of Muslim immigrants. Another public fear that occupies modern German mind is the worry that Islamic culture is taking over Germany. In addition to the observed increase in birthrates attributed to immigrant Muslim communities, there is the spread of Islamic ways of thinking and living among mainstream Europeans and Germans. The idea behind this new anxiety was that Muslim values had already begun to dominate European public culture because liberal Europeans were too permissive to stand up for their values and to protect them (Asad, 2001: 209-227). Like Houellebecq, Broder compares Islam with submission, stating that liberal secular Europeans who submit to Islam's upsurge in Europe have already been submitted (Broder, 2007).

At the same time, Germany is experiencing massive conversions into Islam at a time when Islam is seen as contrary to European values. German mainstream society marginalises converts and questions their national loyalties. In turn, converts try to disassociate themselves from migrants of Muslim-majority countries and promote a denationalised Islam untainted by Turkish or Arab traditions. Some German Muslims believe that once cleansed of its radical conceptions, Islam would correspond to German values and lifestyle (Özyürek, 2015). Prevalent ideas of secular Germany, which defines religion as a sphere separate from all other social realities, in conjunction with the increased racialisation of Muslims, incite converts and other European-born Muslims to promote an Islam deprived of the despised aspects of Middle Eastern values and practices, and fit for secular European and German mindset.

4. The „Great Replacement“ theory of Renaud Camus (L'homme remplaçable, 2012)

„Since when, in history, did a people need 'science' to decide whether or not it was invaded and occupied?“

(R. Camus)

Renaud Camus coined the term „great replacement“ (fr. *grand remplacement*) to show his belief that the native European population is being uprooted by the non-Caucasian immigrants, especially the Muslims. He compares Muslim immigrations to modern colonisation stating that a counterrevolt is bound to happen when white Europeans become aware of the increase in non-white populations (Camus, 2024: 5). Camus began to develop his idea in 1996; while editing a guidebook about the department of Hérault (Occitania, France), he had an epiphany which generated the concept “Great Replacement”. Camus “suddenly realised that in very old villages...the population had totally changed”, and began writing about it (Spectator/Sexton, 2023).

In 2002, Camus founded his own racist political party¹³, *the Parti de l'Innocence*. The party advocates remigration, i.e. sending all immigrants and their families back to the country of their origin, and a complete cessation of future immigration (Onishi, 2019). A decade later, Camus made his theory public by publishing a book under the same title. He explains that the Great Replacement indicates the “replacement of a people, the indigenous French people, by one or others; of its culture by the loss of its cultural identity through multiculturalism”, and adds: “Individuals, yes, can join a people, integrate with it, assimilate to it. But peoples, civilisations, religions – and especially when these religions are themselves civilisations, types of society, almost States – cannot and cannot even want to ... blend into other peoples, other civilisations” (Camus, 2024: 123). He considers that previous generations of European immigrants had been drawn by “love” for France but the newer arrivals since the 1970s, mostly from France's former colonies in the Maghreb and in sub-Saharan Africa, did not come “as friends”. Instead, they came as conquerors and colonizers, filled with hatred and a desire to punish France. Camus singles out Muslims for „not wanting to integrate“ into French society. Camus believes that all Western countries are faced with varying degrees of „ethnic and civilisational substitution“ (Camus, 2024: 125).

A key to understanding Camus' “Great Replacement” theory can be found in his book about aesthetics, titled *Du Sens* („Of Meaning“), published in 2002. Inspired by a dialogue between Plato and Cratylus¹⁴, he wrote that the words “France” and “French” equal a natural and physical reality, not a legal one; it

¹³ A racist party supports white nationalistic ideology that sees white people as a race and seeks to develop and maintain a white racial and national identity. Analysts often use white nationalism interchangeably with white supremacy and white separatism (Author's note).

¹⁴ Plato's work *Cratylus*, is a philosophical text where Socrates discusses the nature of language with Cratylus and Hermogenes. The core question is whether names are conventional (arbitrary, social constructs) or natural (inherently connected to reality). While Cratylus advocates for the natural view, Hermogenes supports the conventionalist view (Jowett, 1892).

is a form of Cratylism similar to Charles Maurras' distinction between the legal country and the real country (Camus, 2002: 23). Camus also built on the earlier work of Jean Raspail, who published the dystopian prophetic novel "The Camp of the Saints" in 1973, about immigration and the destruction of Western civilisation.

As a candidate in the 2012 French presidential elections, Camus repeated some of his political ideas previously expressed in his book, such as serious proposals on repatriation of foreign-born criminals. Yet, he failed to gain enough elected representatives support to be able to run for president, and eventually decided to support Marine Le Pen, the far-right candidate. Three years later, Camus headed an initiative to launch Pegida France, an Anti-Islamist Movement.¹⁵ Although Camus stepped out of the organisation, Pegida France continued operating and organised several anti-immigration and anti-Islam demonstrations. Camus has never diverted from his initial ideological and political course. Thus, in December 2017, he declared: „L'élection présidentielle qui a eu lieu [en 2017] était la dernière chance pour une solution politique. Je ne crois pas à une solution politique (...) car en 2022, cette fois-ci, ce seront les occupants, les envahisseurs, qui feront le vote, qui seront maîtres des élections, donc de toute façon la solution n'est plus politique“ (de Boissieu, 2025).

Determined to make his theory part of the European political programme, in May 2019, Camus ran for the European parliament elections. In his agenda, he wrote: „L'Europe, il ne faut pas en sortir, il faut en sortir l'Afrique...Jamais une occupation n'a pris fin sans le départ de l'occupant. Jamais une colonisation ne s'est achevée sans le retrait des colonisateurs et des colons. La Ligne claire, et seule à l'être, c'est celle qui mène du ferme constat du grand remplacement...à l'exigence de la remigration, ajoutent-ils“ (AFP, 2019). However, international liberal/leftist political fractions occupying government positions see in Camus' ideas harmful racism and anti-Islamism, which is, in their opinion, a direct threat to the socio-political stability in Europe. Thus, in April 2025, when Camus was to participate at the Big Remigration Conference hosted by the UK Homeland Party, the British Home Office denied him entry under the pretext that “his presence in the UK is not conducive to the public good“ (Smith, 2025).¹⁶

¹⁵ Pegida stands for Patriotic Europeans against the Islamisation of the West, and represents a German, anti-Islam, far-right extremist political movement. Pegida offshoots have been formed in various countries, including France. Its main aim is to curb immigration and it accuses authorities of failure to enforce related laws. (Author's note)

¹⁶ Smith, K. (2025). Tweet Post about Renaud Camus. X. 18 April 2025; <https://x.com/KennySmithHP/status/1913260259495248280> (accessed on 18 Sept. 2025)

Since his 2010 and 2012 books (*L'Abecedaire de l'in-nocence/Abecedarium of no-harm* and *Le Grand Remplacement/The Great Replacement*), Camus has been warning of the purported danger of the Great Replacement. The theory supposes that replacist elites are colluding against the White French and Europeans in order to replace them with non-European peoples, specifically Muslim populations from Africa and the Middle East, through mass immigration, demographic growth and a drop in the European birth rate; a supposed process he labelled genocide by substitution (Verstraet, 2017: 58). Camus's replacement theory has been accepted as a manifesto by mostly supremacist and white-nationalist organisations and movements, which has led to several instances of violent attacks targeted mostly at Muslim immigrants. Although Camus has repeatedly condemned any act of violence and terrorism committed in echo with his ideas, dismissing them as “pratiques d'Occupant”,¹⁷ he never opposed their manifesto.

In critique of Camus' white genocide theory, Jean-Yves Camus, an expert on the far right at the French Institute for International and Strategic Affairs, said that Camus viewed the world from the perspective of a novelist and aesthete without recognizing real-world consequences. As noted by Onishi, Camus “should become aware that in our universe, where everything happens in real time, what you say from the position of an aesthete or a writer, can instantly be transformed into a gun and bullets” (Onishi, 2019).

While denying the stigmatisation of all Muslims, Camus believes in an unbroken line between petty crime and Islamic terrorism: „All the terrorists are known by the police, not for terrorist acts or for religious extremism, but by petty larceny and bank attacks, or even by very small things like attacking old ladies in suburban trains, or conflicts between neighbours“. In another speech, he added: “We are talking about the fight against terrorism: in my opinion, there are no terrorists, not a single one. There are occupants who.... kill a few hostages from time to time to better remind us who the master is.” (Spectator/Sexton, 2016).¹⁸

¹⁷ On his Tweet account, Camus wrote: “J'appelle à la révolte anticoloniale, moi, à la décolonisation, à la libération du territoire, au départ de l'Occupant, à son Grand Repatriement qui peut seul nous protéger de la violence – certainement pas au terrorisme et aux massacres de masse, ces pratiques d'Occupant.” (Camus, R. (4 August 2019). Renaud Camus – Twitter. *Twitter*. <https://twitter.com/RenaudCamus/status/1158000063517515778>)

¹⁸ Spectator/Sexton, D. (2023). Enemy of the Disaster: Selected Political Writings of Renaud Camus, reviewed. *The Spectator*. 11 Nov. 2023; <https://www.spectator.co.uk/article/enemy-of-the-disaster-selected-political-writings-of-renaud-camus-reviewed/> (accessed on 18 September 2025)

Camus' hate speech has not gone unnoticed and unpunished. During a conference organised by Bloc Identitaire and Riposte Laique in December 2010, he referred to Muslims as “hooligans” and “soldiers” and “the armed wing of a group intent to conquer French territory and expel the existing population from certain areas”. Consequently, in April 2014, he was fined € 4,000 for incitement to racial hatred. In April 2015, this decision was confirmed by the Court of Appeal in Paris (Le Monde/Staff, 2014; AFT, 2015).¹⁹

Camus sees democracy as a degradation of high culture and favours a system whereby the elite are guardians of the culture, thus opposing multiculturalism. He sees president Macron as a synonym of „forces of replacement“. Macron is someone who thinks of people as „interchangeable“ units within a larger social whole. To Camus this is a very low conception of what being human is. People are not just things. They come with their history, their culture, their language, with their looks, with their preferences. He sees immigration as one aspect of a nefarious global process that renders obsolete everything from cuisine to landscapes. The very essence of modernity is the fact that everything can be replaced by something else.

5. The White Genocide theory of Jean Raspail

“But don't you ever ask yourself what something like this would mean?

The mixture of races, and cultures, and lifestyles?”

“The different levels of ability, different standards of education.

*Why, it would mean the end of France as we know it,
the end of the French as a nation.”*

(The Camp of the Saints, J. Raspail)

“The Camp of the Saints” (*Le Camp des Saints*) is a 1973 French dystopian fiction novel by author and explorer Jean Raspail. As a speculative fiction account, it depicts the destruction of Western civilisation through the Third World mass immigration to France and the Western world. The title “the Camp of the Saints” refers to a passage from the Book of Revelation 20:9),

¹⁹ Le Monde/Staff (2014). L'écrivain Renaud Camus condamné pour provocation à la haine contre les musulmans. *Le Monde*. 10 avril 2014; https://www.lemonde.fr/societe/article/2014/04/10/l-ecrivain-renaud-camus-condamne-pour-provocation-a-la-haine-contr-les-musulmans_4399551_3224.html; AFT (2015). Provocation à la haine contre les musulmans: La condamnation de Renaud Camus confirmée. *20 Minutes*. 9 avr.2015; <https://www.20minutes.fr/societe/1582975-20150409-provocation-haine-contre-musulmans-condamnation-renaud-camus-confirnee>, (accessed on 12 Sept.2025)

where God's people, the Church and the city of Jerusalem are described as being surrounded by hostile nations before being consumed by divine fire. The Old Testament parallel of the Israelite camp in the wilderness serves as a backdrop, signifying a holy encampment under God's direct protection. The novel follows a story of Indian people who desperately want to reach Europe ("a land of plenty") so they board hundreds of ships and head for the promised land. Initially, children of these immigrants were meant for adoption by Belgian citizens, as a form of charity. When the Belgian government realises that the number of Indian children raised in Belgium has reached 40,000 in just five years, an emergency policy attempts to halt the migration. Determined to build a better life, the Indian immigrants are now sailing toward Europe, suffering the worst of conditions while on board, including crowdedness, unsanitary conditions and dismal ambience. As the fleet crosses the Indian Ocean, the political situation in France becomes tense. At a press conference about the crisis, a French official who offers a speech in praise of the immigrants is confronted by a journalist who claims he is merely trying to "feed the invaders" and demands to know if France will "have the courage to stand up to" the immigrants when they reach France. Other journalists seek to inflame tensions between the French and Africans and Arabs already living in the country. They begin to write that the migrant fleet is on a mission to "enrich, cleanse and redeem the Capitalist West". The immigrants eventually disembark on the south of France and make their way north, having no desire to assimilate to French culture, but continuing to demand a First World standard of living, even though they flout laws, do not produce, and murder French citizens. They are joined by the immigrants who already reside in Europe, as well as various left-wing and anarchist groups. Across the West, more and more migrants arrive and have children, rapidly growing to outnumber whites. Soon, the white West has been overrun and pro-immigrant governments have been established, while the white people are ordered to share their houses and flats with the immigrants.

As we can see, *the Camp of the Saints* is a dystopian and apocalyptic work of fiction. A key element of the text is the supposed vulnerability of the West, which has lost its soul to materialism and a fixation on empty things in a period of decline and decay. Native French people are described as "giving in without a blow to the hyperbolic egalitarianism that 'swallows' them down to the rank of third-world men...In such a context, racist deviations are inevitable..." (Moura, 1988:120). Although placed as the centre of the plot, race is not the key issue, but culture and political principles. There are some important truths to be minded, especially in terms of how progressive ideology in the European establishment institutions (state, church, media, academia) disarms people in the face of a hostile and alien culture. The idea

of replacing national with civic society threatens to dilute its identity by immigration.

When first published, Raspail's novel drew the attention of American white supremacists and anti-immigrationists who saw a clear plot's parallel with white genocide conspiracy theory.²⁰ If immigration is left unchecked, the racial character and content of a culture can be undermined to the point of oblivion (Jones, 2018). Raspail was ahead of his time in demonstrating that Western civilisation had lost its sense of purpose and history – its exceptionalism (Owens, 2014). His idea of a monolithic “Western culture” or “Western civilisation” has recently been revived to act in service of immigration restrictionism. The author's main message is that cultures that are completely different in all their principal aspects (history, language, race, religion, education, literature) are beyond assimilation. Autochthonous European culture, if not protected by restrictive policies, is bound to be “replaced” by its non-European invading cultures.

6. Michelle Houellebecq's Declinism theory

*<https://www.theguardian.com/books/2015/sep/06/michel-houellebecq-submission-am-i-islamophobic-probably-yes>
“For these Muslims, the real enemy—the thing they fear and hate—isn't Catholicism.*

*It's secularism. It's laicism. It's atheist materialism. They think of Catholics as fellow believers. Catholicism is a religion of the Book. Catholics are one step away from converting to Islam—that's the true, original Muslim vision of Christianity.”
(Submission, M. Houellebecq)*

Some literary critics also saw the Great Replacement's influence in Michel Houellebecq's 2015 best-seller, “Submission” (fr. *Soumission*), a dystopian novel set in a near-future France where the Muslim Brotherhood wins the 2022 presidential election through an alliance with the Socialists, leading to

²⁰ The white genocide, white extinction or white replacement conspiracy theory is a white nationalist conspiracy theory that claims there is a deliberate plot to cause the extinction of white people through forced assimilation, mass immigration, or violent genocide. It purports that this goal is advanced through the promotion of miscegenation, interracial marriage, mass non-white immigration, racial integration, low fertility rates, abortion, pornography, LGBTQ identities, governmental land-confiscation from whites, organized violence, and eliminationism in majority white countries. This theory is usually brought into relation with the Great Replacement theory (Moses, 2019).

a gradual Islamisation of French society. The story follows François, a lonely literature professor at the Sorbonne, as he navigates this new reality, which includes the introduction of polygamy, the veiling of women, and a shift in academic focus towards Islamic law, all funded by Middle Eastern Islamic countries. The new Islamic government is depicted as a “soft” version of Sharia, focused on restoring traditional morality, family values, and patriarchy, opposing terrorism and fundamentalism.

Although generally accused of being anti-Muslim²¹, the novel is analysed as satirical and politically pessimistic commentary on French identity, the perceived emptiness of modern secular society, and the decline of traditional values. Secular France has given up on its cultural fundamentals and, thus weakened and disbalanced, cannot oppose the strongly rooted Islamic culture and civilisation. The theory that French and European culture are in a state of decline (Declinism) is best reflected in the destiny of the main character François who, seeking an end to his isolation and a sense of meaning, chooses to convert to Islam, finding a form of stability and comfort in the new social order.

Modern malady that has overcome France is anomie:²² the lack of interest in a human being; chronic individualism and spiritual emptiness fathomed by materialistic insatiability; the state of being without faith, as the most crucial element of identity. Houellebecq’s highly visionary depiction places before Europe a post-national era, where European construction is used as a means to dissolve nation states within a superstructure similar to the Roman Empire.

7. Conspiracy theory of Dejan Lučić

*“We are on the brink of civil war between
the European Union and Islam in Germany, France, Italy...
Nostradamus’ prophecy is coming true.”
(Fears of the Powerful, D. Lučić)*

²¹ By cruel coincidence, the book was released in France on 7 January 2015, the day of the Charlie Hebdo Terrorist attacks. The same day the author’s caricature appeared on the cover page of Charlie Hebdo magazine. Houellebecq has a long history with Islam. In one interview in 2002, he called it “the stupidest of all religions” and was charged with inciting racial hatred but later the Paris court dropped the charges. (Author’s note).

²² The sociologist Emile Durkheim popularized the term, in a book on suicide, that reveals the human state of lawlessness, a lack of direction stemming from a lack of governance (Durkheim, 2002).

In his writings, a notorious Serbian conspiratologist, Dejan Lučić, has largely contributed to the promotion of the Great Replacement theory. This is particularly evident in his trilogy “Islamic Republic of Germany” (Fears of the Powerful; British Seal; and Mosad’s Target). The connecting tissue in Lučić’s novels (although never directly) is Camus’ theory that announces the demographic replacement of European population with mostly Muslim immigrants through massive immigration, birthrate reduction and elite policy. The key element of Camus’ theory that Lučić deconstructs in his three books is the Islamisation of Europe as a demographic threat. Lučić artfully weaves a scenario in which Europe, especially Germany, is being deliberately inhabited by Muslims through secret operations, such as “Operation Catapult”,²³ triggering civil war between the European Union and Islam. Lučić directly alludes to Nostradamus’ prophecy of the “green dragon” (symbol of Islam) that conquers Europe through the Balkans (Bosnia and Kosovo) (Reading, 2009: 749-751). Although speculative, Lučić’s novels anticipate “Arabisation and Islamisation” of Europe with Muslims becoming a majority population, who eventually take over the control of Germany and the rest of Europe.

In addition, there is a thin line of constructivism in Lučić’s stories. The author contends that nations or identities are synthetically created for the purpose of controlling territories, weakening other peoples or realising other strategic plans (e.g. masons, illuminati, CIA, or British MI 6). In his trilogy, Lučić claims that Hazars (Turkish-Asian tribe that accepted Judaism around 740 AD) represent the basis for “false Jews” who currently dominate global politics. In his opinion, this is not an organic nation but a synthetic construction of global elite, planning to rebuild “Hazarstan” (a new state in the territory of Caucasus and the Middle East) and destroy Israel and Europe. By stating that 90% of today’s Jews are direct descendants of Hazars, Lučić depicts them as a synthetic hybrid for geopolitical goals. Lučić revealed the plan of rebuilding Hazarstan nine years before the Mosad and the Russian military agency GRU, indicating that such artificially created multicultural societies will eventually lose their national identity.

We see that Lučić’s ideological perspective is deeply rooted in conspiracy theories, wherein synthetic nations are used as a tool for demographic, cultural and political dominance. Although many criticise Lučić’s ideas as

²³ *The Operation Catapult* is Lučić’s literary allusion to the attack on Mers-el-Kébir, a naval base at the coast of French Algeria on 3 July 1940. After the fall of France in 1940, Germany and France concluded armistice. Hence, the British War Cabinet, being apprehensive about the control over the French navy, drafted a plan to neutralise or destroy French ships to prevent them from falling into German hands. A military author and consultant, Ryan Noppen, gives a fascinating analysis of this operation. (Noppen, 2024).

nationalistic and Islamophobic, reality has shown that their nature is deeply prophetic, and rooted not only in Camus' Great Replacement theory but also in "Eurabia" theory of Bat Ye'or.²⁴

7.1. De-Islamisation of Europe?

The concept of "de-Islamisation of Europe" is highly controversial, often tied to far-right, anti-immigrant, and Islamophobic narratives that frame Islam as a threat to European identity or culture. It refers to theories, movements, or proposed policies aimed at reducing the influence of Islam or Muslim populations in Europe, through restricting immigration, remigration, assimilation and integration, or other means. Theories related to "de-Islamisation" often stem from concerns about the perceived "Islamisation" of Europe. In the opinions of some scholars, Islamisation theories are exaggerated or unfounded. They are also seen as the counterbalance to the earlier analysed theories of the great replacement, declinism, and white genocide.

The key theories that support de-Islamisation concept can be divided into political, cultural and demographic. The most prominent political theory is the aforesaid Eurabia conspiracy theory. This theory posits that European elites, in collaboration with Arab powers, are deliberately facilitating the Islamisation of Europe through immigration and multiculturalism, leading to a supposed state of "dhimmitude" (subservience to Islamic rule). It claims Europe is surrendering its culture to Islam, driven by globalist agendas, economic assistance to Muslim countries, and immigration policies (Ye'or, 2005: 147-163).

The most prominent cultural theory is cultural incompatibility. Some narratives assert that Islam is inherently incompatible with European liberal values, such as secularism, democracy, and gender equality. This theory underpins groups like Stop Islamisation of Europe (SIOE), which argue that Islamic practices and political Islam (Islamism) threaten European identity. They advocate for policies to curb Islamic influence, framing their stance as rational rather than prejudiced. Scholars like Bassam Tibi, who proposed a "Euro-Islam" compatible with European values, have expressed pessimism about its adoption, citing the rise of conservative practices like "headscarf Islam" (Илић Духанџија, 2017: 438).

²⁴ Euroabia theory was created by Bat Ye'or, Egyptian-born British-Swiss writer and scholar. The theory was first revealed in her 2005 book "Eurabia: The Euro-Arab Axis." The theory posits that since 1970s, European elites (particularly in France) have pursued a deliberate policy of alignment with Arab and Muslim interests through the Euro-Arab Dialogue. This dialogue has transformed Europe into "Eurabia" characterized by, inter alia, cultural Islamisation (Ye'or, 2005: 147-163).

The demographic theory focuses on the demographic threat that Muslim populations will outnumber non-Muslims due to higher fertility rates and immigration. However, critics argue that this theory ignores declining birth rates among immigrant populations, the rise of non-religious Muslims, and the fact that Muslims remain a minority in Europe (Stonawski, Potančokova, Skirbekk, 2015: 552-567).

These theories have gained traction in certain political and social spheres, driven by specific events and broader societal shifts. Anti-immigrant and anti-Islam sentiments have fueled the rise of far-right parties, such as France's *Rassemblement National* and Germany's *Alternative für Deutschland* (AfD), which performed strongly in recent elections. These parties often link immigration with Islamism, advocating for stricter immigration controls and assimilation policies. Groups like Pegida and its affiliates in Belgium, France, and Germany have organized protests and campaigns against perceived Islamic influence, often citing events like the 2005 Danish cartoon controversy or terrorist attacks, such as Charlie Hebdo in 2015 (Sorkin, 2015).

Anti-Muslim rhetoric has become more visible, with policies like France's 2016 burkini bans and restrictions on religious symbols in public spaces, reflecting efforts to curb visible Islamic practices. These measures are often justified as protecting secularism but are criticised as discriminatory. Furthermore, such measures alienate Muslim communities, increase discrimination, and undermine social cohesion.

High-profile Islamist terrorist attacks (e.g. Paris 2015) have intensified calls for "de-Islamisation" by linking Islam with security threats. For instance, the EU Counter-terrorism Coordinator reported over 5,000 radicals and jihadists travelling to conflict areas in Syria and Iraq, fueling demands for stricter policies (EUROPOL, 2017:12).²⁵ Non-violent expressions of Islamism, such as public displays of banned symbols (e.g. ISIS or Hamas flags) or large-scale street prayers, are also cited as evidence of cultural erosion. Some European governments have pursued policies to create a 'domesticated' Islam aligned with European values, such as France and Germany's efforts to train imams locally and reduce foreign influence on Muslim communities. These policies aim to counter radicalisation but are criticised for oversimplifying Islam's diversity and reinforcing stereotypes (Karoui, 2016: 68-101).

²⁵ EUROPOL (2017). European Union Terrorism Situation and Trend Report (EU TE-SAT Report), 2017, European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation 2017. retrieved on 14 September 2025 from https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/tesat2017_0.pdf

Having all these trends in mind, under the banner of “de-Islamisation”, European governments have proposed and implemented various legal, social and political methods and measures. Many are contentious and face legal or ethical challenges. Limiting immigration from Muslim-majority countries is a core method advocated by groups like SIOE and far-right parties. For example, Poland and Hungary have resisted accepting Muslim immigrants, citing cultural preservation. Cultural assimilation policies, like France’s ban on face coverings (2010) and burkinis (2016), aim to enforce secular norms, often targeting Muslim women’s dress. These policies are created to promote integration but are heavily criticised as restricting religious freedom. Germany and Austria have pushed for “European Islam” through state-sponsored imam training and dialogue forums to align Islamic practices with liberal values. The SIOE and similar groups advocate boycotting companies (e.g. Fisher-Price, KFC) and Muslim-majority countries to reduce economic ties with Islam. They also organize protests to rally against perceived Islamisation. Far-right groups like Pegida use public demonstrations to promote anti-Islam narratives, often clashing with counter-protesters. Some propose countering Islamism through Christian revival or promoting secular values. For example, a New Apostolic Reformation movement suggests a “new Christian reformation” to counter Islamic influence, arguing that secularism has weakened Europe’s cultural defenses (Tabachnick, 2013). Others advocate for counter-narratives to undermine Islamist ideologies, focusing on integrating Muslim populations into Western values rather than excluding them. Increased monitoring of Muslim communities, as seen in France’s tracking of 15,000 individuals linked to Islamist movements, is justified as a security measure but raises concerns about profiling and civil liberties. De-radicalisation programmes, such as those in the UK, aim at reducing extremist influence but they are criticized for targeting Muslims broadly rather than specific threats.

8. Conclusion

Islamisation of Europe as a phenomenon has shown a myriad of faces before the scholars. If put into the context of synthetic nation-building/constructivism, Islamic religion and migration, it will be shaped into a series of mostly conspiracy theories (great replacement, declinism, white nationalism, white supremacism, white genocide, genocide by substitution and many others). The Great Replacement theory has proven to be the most controversial and inflammatory. Is Europe undergoing demogenocide? Who gains most from the process of replacement of everything that is authentically European (culture, language, religion, nation, identity)? To what purpose?

These questions have been placed into the centre of geopolitical discussions of their creators, amalgamating into one common point of interest: nation and national identity. The clerics of mondialism insist on framing nationalism within reactionary fragments of the past, or a pathology of civilizational backwardness. However, current tectonic demographic shifts from the global South toward Europe have revived the natural concept of nationalism, as the only force against final and complete occupation of Europe.

Migrations as a natural process invoke demographic changes. However, such a process, if spontaneous, will result in gradual assimilation and integration, not forceful exclusion and replacement. Muslim immigrants have been divided into two streams, loyalists of political Islam and devout Islamoke-malists. The former have become the cause of critical and oppressive views of European intelligentsia. Often connected to Islamic terrorism, extremist Islamists have endangered the position of European Muslims who are devoted to a Westernised form of Islam, while preserving the bare essentials of traditional Islamic values. The fear of “great replacement” is spreading fast through Europe, reviving strong nationalist ideas for the return to the concept of nation states. As Houellebecq prophesied, Europe can expect two scenarios in near future: Europe should start preparing for the war against Islam or, all conspiracy theories aside, Europe is to experience a “great displacement”, i.e. coexistence of cultures based on “equal, but different” principle.

References

- Adorno, T. (1991). *Culture Industry: Selected Essays on Mass Culture*. ed. J.M. Bernstein. London & New York: Routledge Classics.
- Asad, T. (2001). Muslims and European Identity: Can Europe Represent Islam? in A. Pagden (ed.). *The Idea of Europe: from Antiquity to the European Union*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Berman, R. (2024). Islamism and Immigration in Germany and the European Context. *The Caravan*. 17 September. Retrieved 15 September 2025 from oover.org/research/islamism-and-immigration-germany-and-european-context
- Broder, H. (2007). Hurray! We Are Capitulating. *Der Spiegel Online*. 25 January. Retrieved 12 September 2025 from <http://www.spiegel.de/international/spiegel/0,1518,462149,00.html>
- Camus, R. (2024). *The Great Replacement: Introduction to Global Replacism*. Plieux: Éditions du Château.

Camus, R. (2002). *Du Sens*. Paris: POL.

Connor, W. (1972). Nation-building or Nation-destroying? *World Politics*. 24(3): 319-355. Retrieved 11 September 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.2307/2009753>

Crawford, B. (1996). Explaining Defection from International Cooperation: Germany-s Unilateral Recognition of Croatia. *World Politics*. 48, 4 July.

Ćosić, D. (2008). Islam: pitanja i odgovori. *National Security and the Future*. Udruga sv. Jurja, Zagreb. 9(1-2): 89-121.

Deutsch, K.W. (1963). The Study of Nation-Building, 1962-1966. In K.W. Deutsch & W.J. Foltz (eds), *Nationa-Building* (Forward). Chicago: Adline Atherton.

Deutsch, K.W. (1966). *Nationalism and Social Communication*. Cambridge: MIT Press.

De Benoist, A., Champetier, C. (2000). *Manifesto of the French New Right In The Year 2000*, retrieved from <https://www.4pt.su/en/content/manifesto-french-new-right>

De Boissieu, L. (2025). Parti de l'In-nocence (PI). 4 May. *France-politique*. Retrieved 15 September 2025 from [https://www.france-politique.fr/wiki/Parti_de_l%27In-nocence_\(PI\)](https://www.france-politique.fr/wiki/Parti_de_l%27In-nocence_(PI))

De Weck, J. (2025). France has a problem with racism, not migration. *Inter-nationale Politik Quarterly*. 8 January 2025, <https://ip-quarterly.com/en/france-has-problem-racism-not-migration> (accessed on 11 9.2025)

Durkheim, E. (2002). *Suicide: A Study in Sociology*. London & New York: Routledge.

Ekmečić, M. (2002). *Dijalog prošlosti i sadašnjosti*. Beograd: JP Službeni list SRJ.

Esposito, J. (1999). *The Islamic Threat: Myth or Reality?* New York: Oxford University Press.

EUROPOL (2017). European Union Terrorism Situation and Trend Report (EU TE-SAT Report), 2017, European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation 2017, retrieved from https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/tesat2017_0.pdf

Garand, M. (2019). Immigration in the Context of Religion with Case Studies of France and Hungary. *Honors College*. 524. (accessed on 10 Sept. 2025), https://digitalcommons.library.umaine.edu/honors/524?utm_source=digi-

talcommons.library.umaine.edu%2Fhonors%2F524&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages

Heidegger, M. (1977). *The Question Concerning Technology and Other Essays*. Trans. William Lovitt. New York: Garland Publishing, Inc.

Hamdi, M. E. (1996). The Limits of the Western Model. *Journal of Democracy*. 2(7): 81-85.

Huntington, S. (1996). *The Clash of Civilisations and the Remaking of World Order*. New York: Simon & Schuster.

Илић Духанџија, З. (2017). Евроислам Басама Тибија. *Социолошки преглед*. LI (3): 434-456.

James, E.O. (1961). *Comparative Religion*. London: Methuen & Co.

Јеротић, В. (1999). *Вера и нација*. Београд: Ars Libri.

Jones, S. (2018). The Notorious Book that Ties the Right to the Far Right. *The New Republic*. Washington D.C., 22.2018. <https://newrepublic.com/article/146925/notorious-book-ties-right-far-right> (17.9.2025)

Jowett, B. (1892). *The Dialogues of Plato translated into English with Analyses and Introductions by B. Jowett*. V vol. 3rd ed. Revised and corrected. New York: Oxford University Press.

Калајић, Д. (1994). *Издана Европа*. Београд: Југославијапублик.

Kant, I. (2004). *Critique of Practical Reason*. Trans. Thomas Kingsmill Abbott. Mineola, New York: Dover Publications, Inc.

Karoui, H. E. (2016). *A French Islam is possible*. Paris: Institut Montaigne; [afrench-islam-is-possible-report.pdf](#) (retrieved 9 September 2025)

Kaufmann, E. (2023). The Demography of Islam in Europe; <https://www.s-neps.net/RD/uploads/1-The%20Demography%20of%20Islam%20in%20Europe.pdf> (retrieved 15 September 2025)

Кошутић, Б. (2002). *Увод у велике правне системе данашњице*. Београд: ЈП Службени лист СРЈ

Лучић, Д. (1999). *Исламска Република Немачка 3: Мосадова мета*. Београд: Лагуна.

Лучић, Д. (2000). *Исламска Република Немачка 2: Британски печат*. Београд: Лагуна.

Лучић, Д. (2000). *Исламска Република Немачка 1: Страхови моћника*. Београд: Лагуна.

Moses, A.D. (2019). White Genocide and the Ethics of Public Analysis. *Journal of Genocide Research*. 21 (2): 201 - 213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623528.2019.1599493>

Moura, J. M. (1988). Littérature et idéologie de la migration: "Le camp des Saints" de Jean Raspail. *Revue Européenne des Migrations Internationales*. (in French). 4 (3): 115-124 Retrieved 19 September 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.3406%2Fremi.1988.1182>

Noppen, R.K. (2024). *Mers el-Kébir 1940: Operation Catapult*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.

Onishi, N. (2019). The Man Behind a Toxic Slogan Promoting White Supremacy. *The New York Times*. 20 September 2019; <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/09/20/world/europe/renaud-camus-great-replacement.html> (retrieved 15 September 2025)

Özyürek, E. (2015). *Being German, Becoming Muslim: Race, Religion, and Conversion in the New Europe*. Princeton & Oxford: Princeton University Press.

Owens, M.T. (2014). What an Off-Putting French Novel Can Tell Us about Immigration. *National Review*. 13 June 2014. <https://www.nationalreview.com/2014/06/camp-saints-2014-style-mackubin-thomas-owens/> (accessed on 16 September 2025)

Ramm, C. (2010). The Muslim Makers: How Germany 'Islamises' Turkish Immigrants. *Interventions – International Journal of Postcolonial Studies*. 12(2): 183-197; <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369801X.2010.489692> (accessed on 10 Sept. 2025)

Richter, C., Paasch-Colberg, S. (2023). Media representation of Islam in Germany. A comparative content analysis of German newspapers over time. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*. 8 100619. Retrieved 13 September 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100619>

Qubaisi, S.A. (2025). The Muslim Brotherhood in France: Structures, Influence, and State Response. *Trends Research and Advisory*. 8 June 2025. Retrieved 10 September 2025 from <https://trendsresearch.org/insight/the-muslim-brotherhood-in-france-structures-influence-and-state-response/?srsltid=AfmBOooTMk5XFck-QO5uMZt2Bbki7tkkHf1zd7vrImP-zj6r-5yKu4FH>

Reading, M. (2009). *The Complete Prophecies of Nostradamus*. London: Watkins Publishing

Sorkin, A.D. (2015). Germany's Strange New Right Wing Meets Charlie

Hebdo. *The New Yorker*. 14 January, retrieved on 13 September 2025 from <https://www.newyorker.com/news/amy-davidson/germanys-pegida-meets-charlie-hebdo>

Stonawski, M., Potančokova, M., Skirbekk, V. (2015). Fertility Patterns of Native and Migrant Muslims in Europe. *Population, Space and Place*, 22 (6): 552-567. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.1941>

Tabachnick, R. (2013). The Christian Right, Reborn: The New Apostolic Reformation Goes to War. *Political Research Associates*, 22 March 2013; <https://politicalresearch.org/2013/03/22/christian-right-reborn> (Retrieved 14 September 2025)

Tremblay, M.A. (1993). Ethnic Profile, Historical Processes, and the Cultural Identity Crisis among Quebecers of French Descent. in: M.D. Levin (ed.), *Ethnicity and Aboriginality: Case Studies in Ethnonationalism* (pp. 111-126). Toronto: The University of Toronto Press.

Vattimo, G. (ed.) (2004). *Nihilism and Emancipation: Ethics, Politics, and Law*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Verstraet, A. (2017). C'est ça que tu veux? *Savoirs et Clinique*. 23(2): 55-64. <https://doi.org/10.3917/sc.023.0055>

Ye'or, B. (2005). *Eurabia: The Euro-Arab Axis*. Madison & Teaneck: Fairleigh Dickinson Uni. Press.

Legal documents

United Nations Charter (1945). United Nations Organization, San Francisco; retrieved 10 September 2025 from <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/ctc/uncharter.pdf>

Internet sources

AFP (2019). Européennes: l'écrivain Renaud Camus en tête de liste. Le 9 avril 2019, *Le Figaro*; <https://www.lefigaro.fr/flash-actu/europeennes-le-chantre-de-la-these-du-grand-remplacement-en-tete-de-liste-20190409> (accessed on 16 Sept.2025)

AFT (2015). Provocation à la haine contre les musulmans: La condamnation de Renaud Camus confirmée. *20 Minutes*. 9 avr.2015; <https://www.20minutes.fr/societe/1582975-20150409-provocation-haine-contre-musulmans-condamnation-renaud-camus-confirnee>, (accessed on 12 Sept.2025)

Al-Jazeera/Hafez, F. (2025). State-sponsored Islamophobia in France encourages violence. *Aljazeera*. 5 July 2025. <https://www.aljazeera.com/>

opinions/2025/7/5/state-sponsored-islamophobia-in-france-encourages-violence (accessed on 10 Sept. 2025)

CNN World/Vandoorne, S. (2025). France’s government has collapsed again. How did we get here and what’s next? *CNN World*. 9 September 2025; <https://edition.cnn.com/2025/09/09/europe/frances-government-collapsed-whats-next-intl> (accessed on 10 September 2025).

Le Monde/AFT (2025a), French report warns of spread of Muslim Brotherhood ideology. *Le Monde*. 21 May 2025; https://www.lemonde.fr/en/france/article/2025/05/21/french-report-warns-of-subtle-but-subversive-spread-of-muslim-brotherhood-ideology_6741471_7.html (accessed on 8 Sept. 2025)

Le Monde/AFT (2025b). Macron urges government action on Muslim Brotherhood’s influence in France. *Le Monde*. 21 May 2025; https://www.lemonde.fr/en/france/article/2025/05/21/macron-urges-government-action-on-muslim-brotherhood-s-influence-in-france_6741505_7.html (access 8.9.2025)

Le Monde/Staff (2014). L’écrivain Renaud Camus condamné pour provocation à la haine contre les musulmans. *Le Monde*. 10 avril 2014; https://www.lemonde.fr/societe/article/2014/04/10/l-ecrivain-renaud-camus-condamne-pour-provocation-a-la-haine-contr-les-musulmans_4399551_3224.html (accessed on 12 Sept.2025)

Novi Standard/Mortimer, G. (2023). Francuska u procesu “trećesvetizacije”. (prev. Miloš Milojević), *Novi standard*. 30 јуна 2023; <https://standard.rs/2023/06/30/francuska-u-procesu-trecesvetizacije/?alphabet=latin>, (accessed on 11 September 2025)

Spectator/Sexton, D. (2023). Enemy of the Disaster: Selected Political Writings of Renaud Camus, reviewed. *The Spectator*. 11 Nov. 2023; <https://www.spectator.co.uk/article/enemy-of-the-disaster-selected-political-writings-of-renaud-camus-reviewed/> (accessed on 18 September 2025)

Smith, K. (2025). Tweet Post about Renaud Camus. X. 18 April 2025; <https://x.com/KennySmithHP/status/1913260259495248280> (accessed on 18 Sept. 2025)

Camus, R. (2019). Renaud Camus – Twitter post, 4 August 2019. *Twitter*. <https://twitter.com/RenaudCamus/status/1158000063517515778> (accessed on 18 Sept. 2025)

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**ИСЛАМИЗАЦИЈА ЕВРОПЕ: КОНСТРУКТИВИЗАМ И „ВЕЛИКА ЗАМЈЕНА “–
ИЗМЕЂУ ФИКЦИЈЕ И ФАКЦИЈЕ**

Резиме

Последњих деценија, свијет је постао свједок експанзивних миграција претежно исламског становништва из афричких и блискоисточних земаља на европско тло. Да ли је ово природни процес глобалног кретања људи из већински муслиманских земаља праћен неизбјежним демографским и културним промјенама или је то стратешко остварење Камијеве пророчанске теорије „велике замјене“? Стављањем релевантних дјела фикције (Распај, Бродел, Уелебек, Ками, Ружди, Лучић) у контекст политичког конструктивизма и теорије изградње синтетичке нације (Ђурковић, Калајић, Екмечић), ауторка намјерава да деконструише концепт изградње синтетичке нације који су усвојиле и даље развијале свјетске силе из разлога јачања своје геополитичке позиције на штету слабљења националних држава. и одржавања сталног унутрашњег сукоба. Може се закључити да постоји растућа тенденција злоупотребе религије у сврху изградње новог националног идентитета.

Кључне ријечи: исламизација, конструктивизам, национализам, фикција, прозелитизам, велика замјена.

